

SPEECH MISTAKES IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

Irina Nikolaevna Doronina

teacher of the Department of Russian Philology,
Ferghana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10464755>

Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of speech mistakes in Russian. The author analyzes various types of mistakes that people make when using the Russian language, including grammatical, lexical, phonetic and semantic. The focus is on the causes of these mistakes and how to correct them. The paper also discusses the effects of education, age, social status and other factors on speech error rates. The results of the study can be useful for teachers of the Russian language, linguists and everyone who is interested in studying the Russian language.

Key words and expressions: mistakes, causes, lack, knowledge, rules and structure of the Russian language, use of the Russian language, common type.

Speech mistakes in Russian are a phenomenon that is studied within the framework of psycholinguistics and neurolinguistics. They can be associated with a variety of factors, including stress, fatigue, lack of attention, brain disorders and other causes.

Speech mistakes in Russian can be associated with various aspects, including grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, and speech style. They can occur for various reasons, including lack of education, lack of practice or lack of knowledge about the rules and structure of the Russian language.

1. Grammatical mistakes: This is the most common type of speech error. These may include the misuse of times, cases, genera and numbers, and the misuse of prepositions and conjunctions.

2. Pronunciation mistakes: Russian has a complex system of sounds that can be difficult for speakers of other languages. Pronunciation mistakes may include incorrect stress, incorrect pronunciation of individual sounds, or incorrect use of intonation.

3. Mistakes in vocabulary: This includes the use of incorrect or inappropriate words in a specific context. This can happen when a person does not know the right word or when they confuse words with a similar sound or writing.

4. Stylistic mistakes: These are mistakes related to the misuse of speech style. These may include using too formal or informal a style in an inappropriate

context, using slang or jargon when inappropriate, or using the wrong tone or mood.

5. Syntax mistakes: These are mistakes associated with the construction of sentences. These may include misusing word order, misusing parts of speech, or misusing complex sentence structures.

All these speech mistakes can lead to misunderstanding, distortion of meaning, or even comic situations. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to your speech and strive to improve it.

The level of speech mistakes can be associated with various factors, including education, age, social status, and other aspects.

1. Education: Education plays an important role in the formation of speech skills. The higher the level of education, the less likely it is to make a speech error. This is due to the fact that during the learning process, people learn to build sentences correctly, use complex words and grammatical structures.

2. Age: Age can also affect the rate of speech mistakes. Children and the elderly may have more speech mistakes due to a lack or loss of language skills.

3. Social status: Social status can influence the level of speech mistakes, as people from higher social backgrounds usually have better access to education and resources to improve their speech skills.

4. Other factors: There are other factors that can influence the level of speech mistakes. For example, stress or fatigue can increase the number of speech mistakes. In addition, people whose native language is different from the one they speak may make more mistakes due to a lack of practice or a lack of understanding of grammar.

It is important to note that all these factors can influence the level of speech mistakes, but do not fully determine it. Each person is unique, and their speech skills can evolve differently depending on a variety of factors.

Speech mistakes, such as reservations, rearrangements of sounds or words, substitutions and omissions, can provide valuable information about how the brain processes and produces speech. They may indicate which levels of voice processing are working normally and which may be disrupted.

For example, reservations (unintentional rearrangement of sounds or words) may indicate that the brain is trying to process too much information at the same time, leading to mistakes. This may be useful for diagnosing and treating speech disorders such as stuttering.

Permutations of sounds or words may indicate problems with the planning and coordination of speech movements. This may be useful for diagnosing and treating disorders such as dyslexia or aphasia.

Substitutions and omissions may indicate problems with access to lexical memory or with the formation of speech sounds. This may be useful for diagnosing and treating disorders such as aphasia or dysphasia.

Thus, speech mistakes can serve as an important tool for studying brain function and for the diagnosis and treatment of speech disorders.

Speech mistakes can be caused by a variety of causes, including neurological diseases such as Parkinson's disease, stroke, or brain injury. They can also be linked to mental disorders such as schizophrenia or autism.

Analysis of speech mistakes can help specialists determine which areas of the brain are damaged or working improperly. This, in turn, can help in the development of treatment and rehabilitation strategies.

For example, people with aphasia (a speech disorder caused by brain damage) may make mistakes in word selection or use. Analyzing these mistakes can help specialists determine which areas of the brain are damaged and how it affects speech.

In addition, speech mistakes can serve as indicators of progress in the process of recovery from brain injury or in the treatment of speech disorders. For example, reducing the number of mistakes or changing the type of mistakes may indicate an improvement in the patient's condition.

In general, speech mistakes are an important source of information for neurologists, psychologists and speech therapists. They help improve understanding of brain function and develop new approaches to the treatment of speech disorders.

Analysis of speech mistakes allows specialists to identify disorders in the work of certain areas of the brain responsible for speech. This helps in diagnosing and choosing a treatment strategy.

In addition, the study of speech mistakes can help in the development of new methods for teaching the Russian language for foreigners, as well as in the creation of more effective artificial intelligence systems capable of understanding and reproducing human speech.

Speech mistakes are thus a valuable source of information that helps improve our understanding of brain function and develop new approaches in the fields of medicine, psychology, linguistics and information technology.

References:

1. Doronina, I. N. (2021). Interactive learning and its methodology. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(5), 653-655.
2. Doronina, I. N. (2021). Modernist trends in the literature of the twentieth century: features of futurism and its varieties. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(2), 238-243.
3. Doronina, I. (2021). DISORDERS OF NEUROMOTOR DEVELOPMENT AS AN INDICATOR OF INSUFFICIENT READINESS FOR SCHOOLING.
4. Nikolaevna, D. I. (2022). Innovative Methods Of Teaching Russian Language And Literature. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(6), 581-583.
5. Nikolaevna, D. I. (2021). SOME FEATURES OF STUDYING SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 101-107.
6. Ruslanovna, S. S. (2022). Description of Linguistik Variation Derivation and Use in Russian from the Point of Linguopragmatics. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT*, 1(2), 218-220..
7. Sultanova, S. (2020, December). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. In Конференции.
8. Sultanova, S. (2021). On the definition of the terms "Variology", "Variation", "Variability". *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 2307-2310.
9. Sevara, S., & Timur, A. (2021). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. Chief Editor.
10. Sultanova, S., & Akhmadzhonov, M. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE «LITTLE MAN» IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19 CENTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 52-54.
11. Sultanova, S. R., & Nematov, S. X. (2023). FEATURES OF TURGENEV HEROINES IN THE APPEARANCE OF A MODERN GIRL. FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES, 2(16), 113-117.
12. Султанова, С. Р. (2023). ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПЕЙЗАЖНЫХ ОПИСАНИЙ В СТРУКТУРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(7), 987-992.
13. Sultanova, S., & Akhmadzhonov, M. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE «LITTLE MAN» IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19 CENTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 52-54.

14. Sevara, S., & Nigina, B. (2022). Degrees of Comparison of Adjective Names in Russian and Uzbek Languages. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(10), 105-108.
15. Sultanova, S. (2020, December). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. In Конференции.
16. Sultanova, S. (2021). On the definition of the terms “Variology”, “Variation”, “Variability”. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 2307-2310.